

Benzene-induced Shifts of the ^1H Nmr Spectra of 4-Methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones

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The benzene-induced shifts in the chemical shift values of methyl, methoxyl and aromatic protons have been measured for twelve 4-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones. Their utility in the structure elucidation of this class of compounds has been discussed.

4-Methyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones (4-methylcoumarins) are an important group of natural products, some of them have been found to possess biological activities¹. Benzene-induced solvent shifts of aromatic methoxyl groups have been found to be very useful in the structure elucidation of various classes of polyphenolics, viz. flavonoids², quinones³, isoflavones⁴ and chalcones⁵. We report herein benzene-induced shifts in the ^1H nmr spectra of twelve substituted-4-methylcoumarins (1–12) and their utility in the structure elucidation of natural/new coumarins.

Experimental

4-Methylcoumarins were synthesised via Pechmann condensation of the required phenol and esters. Compounds 1^o, 2⁷, 3⁸, 4^o, 5^o, 6^o, 8¹⁰ and 12¹¹ were prepared by known methods, while compounds 7 and 9–11 were prepared by our reported method¹². The ^1H nmr spectra of the coumarins were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 90MHz spectrometer at 25° and at normal probe, first in CDCl_3 and then in C_6D_6 (TMS internal standard). The magnitude of the solvent shifts is denoted by the symbol $\Delta\delta = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} - \delta_{\text{C}_6\text{D}_6}$ (in ppm).

- 1; R=H, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=OCH₃
- 2; R=H, R₁=OCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 3; R=H, R₁=H, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 4; R=H, R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 5; R=CH₃,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=OCH₃
- 6; R=CH₃,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=OCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 7; R=CH₃,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=H, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 8; R=CH₃,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 9; R=CH₃,CH₂,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=OCH₃
- 10; R=CH₃,CH₂,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=OCH₃, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 11; R=CH₃,CH₂,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=H, R₂=OCH₃, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H
- 12; R=CH₃,CH₂,COOCH₂,CH₃,
R₁=H, R₂=H, R₃=OCH₃, R₄=H

Results and Discussion

When benzene is used as the solvent for recording the spectra of polar solute molecules, some protons show larger shifts than the others, when compared with the spectra taken in an inert solvent (CDCl_3 , CCl_4). The protons lying in the region of high electron density tend to be deshielded in benzene, while those in the region of low electron density are shielded. In presence of a C-5 OCH_3 group, the C-4 methyl group in 4-methylcoumarins shows^{1,8} benzene-induced shift of ~ 0.38 – 0.40 , which increases to 0.63 – 0.80 in the absence of the C-5 OCH_3 group. We have observed similar type of benzene-induced shifts (Table 1) in compounds 1–12; the C-4 methyl group showing a large shielding ($\Delta\delta = 0.70$ – 0.80 ppm) in 1, 3 and 4. This is due to the $-R$ effect of the C-2 carbonyl function. The C-4 carbon becomes partly electron-deficient and exerts $-I$ effect on the methyl group attached to it, with the result that this methyl gets shielded by benzene. As the C-5 methoxyl group is in conjugation to the C-2 carbonyl function, benzene associates primarily at this group and can not exhibit the same amount of shielding on the C-4 methyl as it could in the absence of a C-5 OCH_3 function. But in compounds 5–12 having (ethoxycarbonyl)alkyl sidechain at the C-3, the benzene-induced shift for the C-4 methyl group is again diminished. The reason could be that the negative dipole-end of the ester carbonyl function is in close proximity of the C-4 methyl group and hence the approach of benzene molecule to this methyl group is impeded.

The benzene-induced shifts (0.20 – 0.26 ppm) of the C-8 methoxyl function were much lower than those of methoxyl groups present at C-5, C-6 or C-7 (0.50 – 0.80 ppm) (Table 1). This may be due to the benzene-association at both the pyrone ring oxygen and the C-7 OCH_3 group, as a result of which the approach of benzene to the C-8 OCH_3 group would be diminished. Thus the magnitude of the C_6D_6 -induced shifts can be useful in the location of a substituent at the C-3, C-5 and C-8 positions.

The aromatic proton shifts induced by C_6D_6 were also investigated in all the 4-methylcoumarins

TABLE 1—NMR CHEMICAL SHIFT VALUES (δ) AND BENZENE-INDUCED UPFIELD SHIFTS (IN PARENTHESIS) OF DIFFERENT METHYL AND METHOXYL GROUPS IN THE COUMARINS (1–12)

Compd. no.	C-4 CH ₃	C-5 OCH ₃	C-6 OCH ₃	C-7 OCH ₃	C-8 OOH ₃
1	2.39(0.69)			3.98(0.62)	3.98(0.26)
2	2.45(0.38)	3.80(0.78)		3.80(0.65)	
3	2.40(0.80)		3.91(0.61)	3.92(0.81)	
4	2.40(0.79)			3.87(0.72)	
5	2.38(0.49)			3.91(0.51)	3.91(0.21)
6	2.46(0.20)	3.82(0.64)		3.80(0.55)	
7	2.36(0.56)		3.91(0.54)	3.91(0.72)	
8	2.34(0.49)			3.84(0.56)	
9	2.35(0.52)			3.90(0.58)	3.90(0.20)
10	2.52(0.22)	3.84(0.67)		3.80(0.61)	
11	2.40(0.52)		3.90(0.52)	3.90(0.70)	
12	2.38(0.48)			3.81(0.53)	

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL SHIFT VALUES (δ) AND BENZENE-INDUCED UPFIELD SHIFTS (IN PARENTHESIS) OF DIFFERENT AROMATIC PROTONS IN THE COUMARINS (1–12)

Compd. no.	H-3	H-5	H-6	H-8
1	6.09(0.26)	7.30(0.62)	6.89(0.59)	
2	5.85(0.17)		6.19(0.29)	6.32(0.22)
3	6.12(0.29)	6.92(0.54)		6.80(0.42)
4	6.07(0.27)	7.43(0.70)	6.74(0.24)	6.85(0.30)
5		7.28(0.48)	6.82(0.44)	
6			6.24(0.24)	6.30(0.18)
7		6.96(0.54)		6.80(0.47)
8		7.53(0.58)	6.79(0.36)	6.90(0.32)
9		7.22(0.48)	6.77(0.42)	
10			6.35(0.26)	6.45(0.18)
11		6.88(0.40)		6.70(0.35)
12		7.39(0.44)	6.68(0.18)	6.80(0.20)

(Table 2). All protons were shielded in C_6D_6 relative to CDCl_3 . Minimum shielding occurred for the H-3 (0.17–0.29 ppm) as this position is not conjugated to the C-2 carbonyl function. The shielding of H-6 was found to be quite less in compounds 2 (0.29 ppm) and 4 (0.24 ppm) compared to 1 (0.59 ppm). The increase in the benzene-induced shift for the H-6 in compound 1 may be because of the 7,8-dimethoxy substitution pattern; in order to minimise the steric repulsion, the C-7 OCH_3 group is oriented towards C-6 and being in conjugation with the C-2 carbonyl function associates to a good extent with benzene causing upfield shift of H-6. Similarly, the $\Delta\delta$ values of H-6 in compounds 5 and 9 were found much higher compared to those in 6 and 8, and in 10 and 12, respectively. In case of 5,7-dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarins 2, 6 and 10, the benzene association at H-6 and the resultant $\Delta\delta$ (0.24–0.24 ppm) will be less because of the steric hinderance of the two flanking-benzene associated methoxyl groups. The extent of $\Delta\delta$ value of H-6 can thus differentiate 7,8-dimethoxylation pattern from 5,7-dimethoxylation in 4-methylcoumarins.

Similarly, the benzene-induced solvent shift for the H-8 was also found higher in compound 3 (0.42 ppm) compared to compounds 2 (0.22 ppm) and 4 (0.30 ppm). The C-7 OCH_3 in 3 is associated and causes large shielding for the H-8 as in compound 1. Also the $\Delta\delta$ values for the H-8 in compounds 7 and 11 were found much higher than in 6 and 8, and in 10 and 12, respectively. Thus the extent of the $\Delta\delta$ value for the H-8 can help in discerning the 6,7-dimethoxylation pattern in 4-methylcoumarins.

We have also recorded the benzene-induced shifts of different methyl and methoxyl groups, and those of aromatic protons in a (1 : 1) mixture of C_6D_6 and CDCl_3 (Table 3). As expected these values were found to be different from those observed in pure C_6D_6 .

TABLE 3—BENZENE-INDUCED SHIFT VALUES OF AROMATIC PROTONS, METHYL AND METHOXYL RESONANCES OF THE COUMARINS (1–12) IN A MIXTURE OF BENZENE–CHLOROFORM

Compd. no.	$\Delta\delta^*$								
	C-4 CH ₃	C-5 OCH ₃	C-6 OCH ₃	C-7 OCH ₃	C-8 OOH ₃	H-3	H-5	H-6	H-8
1	0.45			0.42	0.19	0.24	0.40	0.38	
2	0.40	0.66		0.59		0.22		0.34	0.24
3	0.41		0.40	0.51		0.21	0.41		0.29
4	0.40			0.34		0.17	0.58	0.17	0.23
5	0.34			0.49	0.13		0.43	0.32	
6	0.26	0.55		0.49				0.32	0.26
7	0.58		0.57	0.71			0.54		0.48
8	0.42			0.48			0.52	0.27	0.27
9	0.23			0.28	0.07		0.24	0.24	
10	0.26	0.67		0.61				0.33	0.29
11	0.39		0.38	0.56			0.30		0.24
12	0.45			0.53			0.47	0.24	0.28

* $\Delta\delta(\text{ppm}) = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} - \delta_{\text{C}_6\text{D}_6}$.

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